

4Q52 (4QSam^b) frag. 4 + IAA Plate 18, frag. 45 (1 Samuel 16:1-11)

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The editors of the Qumran Cave 4 manuscript 4Q52 (4QSam^b) published twenty-three identified fragments of this manuscript which might be the oldest existing manuscript of a biblical book. (DJD 17, 219-46). One of the hitherto unidentified fragments from Qumran Cave 4, PAM 43.686 frag. 65 (DJD 33, Pl. XXVI) referenced in the IAA's The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Library as Plate 18, Frag 45, should be assigned to 4Q52 and joins to the top of 4Q52 frag. 4. I propose to refer to this fragment as 4Q52 frag. 24.

Join (GIMP) of LLDSSDL Plate 18, Frag. 45 and Plate 206, Frag. 1

Images: Screen captures from

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-501197>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-359754>

Photographer: Shai Halevi

On the basis of the long tail of a letter, the 4Q52 editors had already surmised that the first word of the first line of 4Q52 frag. 4 would have been אשלחך, of which only part of the *kap* remained (DJD 33, 226-27). Plate 18 frag. 45 (PAM 43.686 frag. 65) confirms this, and provides the letters אשל, and some remains of ח. In the top line of Plate 18 frag. 45 (PAM 43.686 frag. 65) only part of מר remains, which should reflect the first word of 1 Sam 16:1-11

The first three lines of the joined fragments may therefore be transcribed as follows:

[ויא]מרן יהוה אל שמואל עד מתי אתה מתאבל אל שאול ואני מאסתיו ממלך על ישראל מלא קרנך שמן ולך]
[אשלחך] אל ישי בית לחם כי ראיתי בבניו לי מלך ויאמר שמואל איך אלך ושמע שאול והרגני ויאמר יהוה עגלת]
בקר קח בידך ואמרת לזבח ליהוה באתי וקראת לישי לזבח ואנכי אודיעך את אשר תעשה ומשחת לי את אשר]

The hitherto unidentified fragment attests to a new paragraph starting at the beginning of a new line.

Bibliography

- DJD 17 Frank Moore Cross, Donald W. Parry, Richard J. Sailey, and Eugene Ulrich, *Qumran Cave 4, XII: 1-2 Samuel*. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 17. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2005
- DJD 33 Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001.